

THE IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY SECONDARY EDUCATION IN INDIA**Caroline Lepcha¹&Dr. Sanat Kumar Rath²***Research Scholar¹ Asst.Professor**Department of Eduaction Vinaya Bhavana,Visva Bharati**Santiniketan-731235,Bolpur,West Bengal, India***Abstract:**

Quality is trust worthy; it provides standard and excellence to the product so that we can be assured what we are purchasing. It makes us satisfied and reliant, so quality education does the same with the individual. It brings out what the individual has well within himself/herself. Quality education perfectly understands the thirst of an individual and provides fulfilling the need of the individual. Now a day in any area educational qualification alone is not sufficient but the requirements have gone far and wide.

The outcome process of quality education can not only be seen but can be felt by the individual and the society. Quality education makes the individual to face the challenges and help to solve them by bringing out the best in an individual. Quality education is the best gift that the individual can get from the parents, teachers and school administrators.

Key words: *Quality, Education*

The best quality a mankind possesses is to learn and to acquire knowledge. In everyday of our life we tend to be more wise than yesterday, whether learning is accidental or intentional our knowledge are never limited, it grows with our age, experience and will. Hence, sending to school is the best gift for any child by his/her parents. So education is the unending present to use for whole life. Education gives beautiful turn to our life; it fills with courage, value, ethics, independence, respect, and self awareness, so on. Education is the birth right to every individual and it is the responsibility for every citizen to attain at least the basic schooling. Education nurtures the mind and soul of the individual so that he/she has the life of his own. Like the porter shapes and moulds his clay into a beautiful pot education shapes and moulds an individual into a balanced personality.

The constitution of India under the Article 45 clearly directed the state to “*endeavour to provide, within a period of ten years from the commencement of this constitution, for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years.*” India is in the state of achieving one of the developed countries. Every day we talk about new discoveries, achievements, technologies, space and

stars so on. However there is still other side of the country who do not have the privilege to attain the school. What are the problems behind? many individual have to make livelihood as the priority rather than education, there are many individual who are dropouts, poverty is the reason for many individuals, some individual indulge in drug addiction and some individual become prey of discrimination. Studies suggest that “*achievement of education –from primary to upper primary and upper primary to secondary –has a clear motivational impact on the parents and children towards acquiring school education.*”

To provide the opportunity of education is like to plant the seed of which gives sweet fruit all round the year. But for the sweet fruits a planter has to take care and nurture. So the child too has to be taken care for its needs. It is about the third of our population belongs to the age group of 0-14. These citizens contribute to be one of the greatest investments and have the perfect hand for the country’s well being. They belong to the very important persons of the country because what they learn today, they will act tomorrow.

Well India was laid back to act for the commitments toward universal elementary education which is obviously has a great impact on acquiring secondary education as well. According to the Secondary Education Commission 1952-53 “... This is however the stage which marks the completion of education for the large majority of pupils. It is the secondary schools that supply teachers to the primary schools and students to the university. An inefficient system of secondary education is, therefore, bound to be affected adversely the quality of education at all stages.” Education must be of the quality, without standard education the whole system will be affected. Quality covers the whole educational system by giving satisfying outcome.

Meaning of Quality Education

The word *quality* is widely known and it came the Latin word *qualis* means *what kind of*. Excellence or standard are the general meaning of quality. Before purchasing any product a consumer checks for the quality first, quality product not only give satisfaction but can use for the long time. Likewise quality education provides satisfaction and brings out the innate abilities the person has. Quality education changes the whole educational system without damaging the good which education has. Quality education is simple step towards progress and development of oneself and a nation as a whole. Quality education is the major concern for the parents, teachers and the school administrator. If a child do not grow with the quality education than the whole system of education along the country will suffer.

Narula (2006) writes on *Quality in School Education and Role of Education Board* quality of secondary education would require inputs from the boards to develop dialogue with the state government to strengthen in integrate and cohesive manner.

For the effective outputs results of quality education the input of quality education is very necessary to understand clearly.

Vineesha V.and Nath (2009) conducted a study on *Quality Enhancement in View of Rashtriya Madhmic Siksha Abhiyan*. The objective of the study was to focus on the implementation of Rashtriya Madhmic Siksha Abhiyan. The study found out RMSA's goal is to establish a common school system by establishing enough number of secondary schools. Qualities of both instructional as well as infrastructural aspects would be provided. Equity for social disadvantaged groups, girls and differentially able groups were included in the programme. Rashtriya Madhyamik Siksha Abhiyan vision is to provide good quality education, universal access, equity and to establish a common school system. The overall enhancement on quality of school in the state is given importance in a significant way.

Muhammad (2009) conducted a *Comparative Study of Quality of Education in Public and Private secondary school*. The objective of the study was to compare the public and private quality in education. Main findings of the study were: that private sector schools had actually less number of students and teachers at secondary level as compared to public sector schools. The results of 10th class students in boards' examinations of private schools were better than government schools. While with respect to ownership of building, almost 98% public sector schools had their own buildings and majority of private schools was running in rented buildings. In public sector schools student-teacher ratio was higher than private schools. Heads of private sector secondary schools were better than heads of public sector secondary schools regarding involvement of subordinate staff in decision making, keeping themselves as a part of team while leading them and carrying out the well- organized tasks. But the heads of public sector secondary schools were more qualified academically as well as professionally, having more administrative experience as compared to private sector secondary schools' heads. Teachers of public secondary schools were more qualified academically as well as professionally having command over teaching Methodology as compared to the teachers of private secondary schools. In public schools, in service training the quality education is an indispensable and inevitable agent for change as education is a process of civilization and development.

The overall school system contribute great essence in the quality education; every trained teachers, their ratio, school infrastructure, school boards etc can add some amount in making the school of quality.

Besley (2009) writes on *Assessing the Quality of Educational Research in Higher Education* “the search for the perfect form of quality assessment may still be on, but nevertheless remains elusive.” The book focuses on the theoretical and practical issues especially in higher education. Further she divided the book into four chapters which are- i) Neoliberalism, performance and the assessment of educational research quality ii) Internationalization and the Assessment of Research Quality in Education iii) Research governance by evaluation iv) Assessing the Quality of Research in Higher Education.

Research in education helps to know the existing problem and bring many possibilities to solve the problems which are going. Through quality research the ongoing work and achievement in the institution can be found.

Ramalingam (2010) mention on *Quality Assurance through Professional Development of Teachers* that among the many parameters to reach the quality education the professional teachers help to achieve the quality education in classroom.

There are many problems which block to create bridge between the quality and intuition. Teachers are the true transformer of knowledge and these teachers need to be trained and have ethic for the teaching profession. Only the teachers with great quality can fulfil the dream of quality education.

Ka-shing (2011) conducted a case study on *Effectiveness of an International Curriculum in providing Quality Education* to students. The objectives were i) to study about an international curriculum and its rationale ii) to check upon the adaptation of international education which would provide quality education to the students’ future and iii) to know a local school deliver as the key elements of an international curriculum. The study found out that it is by and large effective to implement an international education curriculum for students.

Curriculum is the important part of learning. And without which it is impossible to match the personality of present world. A revised curriculum can bring a lot to the individual for the future life.

Historical Background of Secondary Education

Since the very beginning secondary education merely has become the gateway to the higher education. India has been contributing the knowledge in all areas when even the schools had not been invented; the *risis* and *munis* have started imparting knowledge in *gurukulas* far away in the forest. In those times there was no interference by the state nor was the kings. Which was directly managed by the teachers / gurus and students / shishyas. The battle of Plassy and the grant of Diwani made not only the British to rule in India but also rule in education system as well. So this is how modern education started in India and brought tremendous change in the history of Indian education. The board of secondary education plays the

prominent features in providing the future scenario of the individual. As examination is the integral part and its success depends on the board of the school. Through Dispatch of Charles woods in the colonial period gave much importance to higher education than the primary and the secondary education. But it resulted in the board of secondary education to safeguard the quality of education. It was in the 14th session on January 1948 the commission was set up by the Central Advisory Board to check and to give quality. Secondary education of that period was of no quality and needed through investigation. Government of India for the first time after the independence appointed the commission which is called *Mudaliar commission or Secondary Education Commission on September 1952* under Dr. A Lakshmanswami Mudaliar with eight other members. The Commission studied throughout the country from October 1952- June 1953 and submitted the report on 29th August 1953. According to the report *education is essential for the success of democracy and effective citizenship*. The report is very important in the history of India as with this the Secondary Education Commission was accepted by the government. After the commission new pattern of school education was set up. The structure of the new pattern system were 11 years of school education that is 5 years of primary, 3 years of middle school and 3 years of higher secondary. The secondary school students were between 11-17 ages. The commission changed the curriculum too as the old curriculum was theoretical and bookish and did not match with the existing lifestyle and the society. According to Dr. BR Purkait it was “single track” narrow and has no goal. The new curriculum was with the interest and need of the individual along with the varied courses. It was practical and with the growing need of the society without forgetting the abilities of the learner. Discipline was given importance for both the teachers and the students with the good quality of teaching methods so that the school could attain the certain quality. The All India Council for secondary Education (AICSE) came up with the three basic areas- examination reform, in-service teacher education and science education. In 1959 AICSE renamed as Directorate of Extension Programmes for Secondary Education (DEPSE) for giving full attention to secondary education. The National policy on education 1968 made various principles on such one principle also gave emphasis on the opportunity to be provided at the secondary education because it is the instrument of social change and transformation. Quality of school education is the most important concern for everybody. To deal with the certain issues government of India in 1977 conducted a survey and found the present position of secondary schools need to be restructured. The National Policy of Education 1986 gave immense focus on the secondary education and for its quality along with the quantitative expansion. In 2009 Ministry of Human Resource Development

of India started the project called RMSA for the development of the secondary schools. The vision of RMSA is to provide quality education throughout the country.

Aims of Secondary Education

Aim is the key aspect for any plan; aims without plan are dominated by other eternal force and become weak to reach. Secondary education as well needs the plan to survive and attain the quality. The aims of secondary education are-

1. To improve, transform and clear the thinking of the individual.
2. Impart education with the need and interest of the learner.
3. To create leadership skill.
4. To foster democratic citizenship.
5. Education must have value based and problem solving education.
6. Education must go with the changing aspect of society.
7. To give focus on practical vocational education.
8. To develop the personality of the individual.
9. To promote equality and equity.
10. Dignity of labour.

Problems of Secondary Education

Historically compared to the secondary education in India was much poorer than the primary and higher education. Still lots of attention are needed to touch the level of quality. There is no wrong to say that every stage of education is equally important than the other. Each level of education has its own kind of uniqueness and features. But somewhere in between we failed to give proper attention to secondary education. Adolescence is also one of the crucial periods of human being, we cannot ignore it. And this adolescence happens to be the part of the secondary education culture. If they are left behind than the country suffers till the end.

The foul and unhealthy environment of the school is another important factor that hampers to promote in imparting quality education. Sometimes interference in the school premises by political parties creates confusion in the young minds of individuals. Drugs, discrimination, indiscipline, non-academic activities and other addiction leads to the polluted environment.

Secondary education no doubt promotes literacy but fails to impart skilled education and this hampers the overall economy of the country. The present secondary education system also suffers because it gives least

importance to vocational education and training. As vocational education and training create balance between the academic and the world of works.

Well equipped classes and good teaching materials have to be provided because our schools are overcrowded and many individual in the classroom does not enjoy the teaching learning facilities and stopped coming to schools. Some schools in our country do not have black/green boards, chairs, tables and proper classroom. The method of imparting education is traditional and not according to need of all the students.

It also needs keen reflection to the curriculum and syllabus, as it is theoretical and not productive. Present curriculum and syllabus of the secondary schools needs to be clear and inspiring. The dull curriculum and syllabus can cause damage to the institution and nation as a whole.

The teacher holds special place in the field of education. He is the maker and the destroyer. So the teacher must be trained. An untrained teacher cannot solve the classroom problems. Some schools still have untrained teachers, who do not understand the noble character in teaching.

Today's world has so changed that technology do not spare none. In that way co-curricular activity has no room for the individual in the secondary schools. They give least importance to co-curricular activities. Co- curricular activities build up the physical as well as mental fitness of the individual.

Poverty is serious problem in the country, which cannot be keeping aside. Though the present condition of the expenditure has increased and education has become expensive too but an individual cannot be ignored by the privilege of quality education.

The increasing population in the secondary classroom is the major concern which has to be taken care of. Increase in population does not mean that an individual has no rights for quality education rather each individual needs to be count as an important for the growth of the country. The growing pupil ratio in the secondary schools has become the major problem these days. An over-crowded classroom is creating great suffer in the hands of the teacher. These days due to the higher ratio in secondary schools the teacher fails to contact and understand the student.

There is little scope for leadership building in secondary education so, character building for the leader is an important aspect of an individual and this character building will get help to come out by the secondary school. Future leaders should not vanish in the dark rather they should get enough opportunity to shape their talents.

The success of secondary schools lies also in the hand of quality administrators. The poor and indiscipline administrators do not provide enough opportunities to reach the goal of the school.

Sometimes problems of quality in education also lie when the individual is not taking the advantage of provided facilities given to them. The individual do not attend school or has been drop out because the individual thinks that the present system of education is not relevant to his/her need.

Importance of Quality Secondary Education

Secondary education being in between the primary and higher education has the strong responsibility for all, whether it is for the parents, teachers, students and the government so on. It decides the career and the future of the individual. As the Secondary Education Commission 1952-53 says it provides teachers to the primary schools and students to the university. Without quality education a secondary schools will be empty and incomplete. It is so important that it goes beyond the curriculum to fulfil the needs of the individual. Secondary education should not be left out and should be given equal opportunity like primary and higher education. It was in the 1952 the Secondary Education Commission or Mudaliar Commission was set up to check on the progress of secondary education. If secondary education fails to provide quality based education then the country fails too.

The most important stage of human life as the adolescence falls on the secondary education, so the schools must be very careful regarding the imparting education. In this period school plays very important role in the life of the individual. An individual here finally learns to build his /her own world and try hard to fulfil it. If the school help in any how or any way he/she touch the foot of success. Hence the future of the individual is in the hand of schools. Quality education comes close with the overall situation in the schools and covers the growing need in education. It provides full fledged education so that no individual should be left in its account. Every day is the new beginning and every sunrise brings hope, so quality education acts same like the new day in the field of education. It is an educational revolution and has power to change the society.

Environment in the secondary schools plays the most important role, if the school provides the quality environment; where the gender biasness is free, free from drug addiction, peaceful healthy and clean naturally any individual can attain the school without hesitations. As the quality education also provides the good and healthy environment, it makes an individual clear in thought and mind.

It is the secondary education which enlightens an individual for the future career and provides growth according to their interest in the respective fields. Here an individual has become fully develop to choose his/her field of interest, that's why it is very important that the secondary education must be of quality. As quality education makes skilled in labour and educated, this is the great demand of the present world.

Secondary education too has its importance like the primary and the higher education. But lost its importance when the priority is given only to the primary and the higher education. Like a well equipped schools, quality secondary education has to advanced well equipped. Quality class are the rights for every individual who comes to the schools every morning with the dreams in the eyes.

The curriculum and syllabus of the secondary education must help to meet the quality goals. The planned curriculum and syllabus not only teach the knowledge but also foster good classroom activities and conduct good examination to evaluate widely in boards.

Quality secondary schools have the trained teachers which help the young citizens of the secondary schools to easily understand the problems, need and the demands of the individual. These trained teachers are their guide and philosopher who provide education with the need of interest and make them aware to use their intellect to solve the problem which now they have and as well later in their life. In order to create harmonious living of the individual these quality teachers also makes aware of the talents the individual have and show the way how to use and polish those talents.

Quality education focuses on the development of head to toe of the individual. It knows what co-curricular activities could bring in the individual's life. It is also through the co-curricular activities the quality fulfil its aims.

If the quality has its major job to do is about the growing student teacher ratio and this has added as major concern in the quality education. Quality education promotes the learning with the perfect teacher student ratio so that every individual get required attention in the classroom.

The secondary education is well known for its leadership training and character building. Quality education provides enough opportunities so that no individual is left behind in the crowd for the enhancement of capability. Scouts, Guides, NCC, NSS, and Clubs etc help to enhance the talents and character in the individual.

The quality of the school does not depend only on the student, teacher and school environment, rather can be achieve through the school administrator. Quality administrator provides quality in the school premises and plant the seed of quality all the year and future to come.

School represent the society and the individual here learns how to act and behave the individual. The most important aim of education is to make the individual to learn. Quality education gives quality behaviour, it transfer the heart of discipline to the individual. The individual acts and copy as the other individual does and eventually the whole school behave so.

Conclusion

The importance of quality education is more than what is seen with the naked eyes. The existing education must meet all the demands which the individual need. With the help of opportunities provided by quality education an individual get enough space to grow and develop. Quality education brings closer to everyone in the school so that the future remains same. Secondary education cannot be ignored because it is the important stage in the system of education. It decides the character, goal and future of the individual. Quality secondary education inculcates harmonious development in the individual to promote him/her and nation as a whole.

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